

Economic growth and Sustainable Development: What do the Sustainable Development Goals tell us?

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Context	3
1.2	Definition and Brief History of Sustainable Development	3
1.3	Literature Review	5
1.4	Methodology	6
1.4.1	Research Objectives and Hypotheses	6
1.4.2	Principal Component Analysis (PCA)	6
1.4.3	Econometric Model	7
2	Descriptive Statistics	9
2.1	Sources of Data and Dataset Cleaning	9
2.2	Data Availability	11
2.3	GDP per Capita and SDG Scores	12
2.4	Preliminary Analysis of SDG Interlinkages	13
3	Data Modelling and Analysis	14
3.1	Principal Component Analysis	14
3.2	Clustering	20
3.2.1	HCA	20
3.2.2	Clusters in lights of socioeconomic and politico-cultural structures	23
3.3	Linear Regressions	25
3.3.1	Objective and Modelling Strategy	25
3.3.2	Selection of Explanatory Variables	25
3.3.3	First Regression: log(GDP per capita PPP) on Principal Components	26
3.4	Economic interpretation of the principal-component coefficients	28
3.4.1	Model Optimization: Stepwise Variable Selection	29
3.4.2	Model Interpretability: Towards More Readable Regressors	31
3.4.3	Limitations of SDG Scores and Performance Indicators	33
3.4.4	Temporal Dynamics Exploration	33
4	Conclusion	35
4.1	Discussion	35
4.2	Future Research	35
	Appendices	36
A	Methodological research design	36
B	SDG Wedding Cake	37
C	Correlation circles	38
D	Extended Summary Statistics : Clustering Characterization	41
E	Distribution of Selected Exogenous Variables Across Clusters	42

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

In 2024, during COP29 in Baku, developing nations called for \$1.3 trillion in climate financing to meet urgent adaptation and mitigation needs. Yet, the final agreement secured less than a quarter of that demand, exposing the widening gap between global ambitions and the realities of international solidarity. Meanwhile, the United Nations' 2024 SDG Report revealed that only 17% of targets are currently on track, raising concerns about the feasibility of achieving the 2030 Agenda.

These setbacks emphasize the growing need to better understand how countries progress across the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and how different dimensions of development interact. Beyond moral or political imperatives, identifying structural patterns in SDG dynamics is essential for optimizing public policies and resource allocation.

Recent research has increasingly focused on the interconnections between SDGs rather than analyzing each goal in isolation. Jean-Pierre Cling and Clément Delecourt (2023) notably applied Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) to highlight strong structural links between human development goals (such as poverty reduction, education, and health) and economic indicators. Their work also revealed weaker internal consistency among environmental SDGs, suggesting fragmented approaches to ecological sustainability.

Complementary studies, such as those by Nilsson et al. (2018) and Iacobuta et al. (2022), have further stressed the importance of identifying synergies and trade-offs among SDGs to better target interventions. These findings encourage the use of multivariate and dimensionality-reduction techniques, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or clustering, to uncover underlying development trajectories.

1.2 Definition and Brief History of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development refers to a model of economic growth that reconciles the imperatives of environmental sustainability, social justice, and economic efficiency. This concept is based on the idea that meeting present needs should not compromise the ability of future generations to meet their own. While the modern expression "sustainable development" was officially established in 1987 by the Brundtland Report, its origins are rooted in an older economic reflection on the interactions between growth, natural resources, and collective well-being.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) comprise a set of 17 global objectives adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in September 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. They succeed the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), established in 2000, and aim to eradicate poverty, protect the planet, and ensure prosperity for all by 2030. Unlike the MDGs, which primarily targeted developing countries, the SDGs involve all nations, recognizing the necessity of international cooperation to achieve balanced and sustainable development. Their implementation relies on regular monitoring through indicators measuring progress, as well as the mobilization of governments, the private sector, and civil society.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Figure 1: The 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Each goal (or SDG) typically comprises between 8 and 12 targets, and each target is associated with one to four indicators used to measure progress toward its achievement.

The concept of sustainable development progressively emerged during the late 20th century through major international initiatives. The Stockholm Conference (1972) and the Brundtland Report (1987) formally introduced the idea of balancing economic growth, environmental protection, and social equity. Throughout the 1990s, global efforts to institutionalize sustainability led to landmark agreements such as the Rio Declaration (1992) and the Kyoto Protocol (1997). Building on these foundations, the United Nations adopted the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in 2000, targeting poverty reduction, education, and health. The 2015 Paris Agreement represented a turning point in climate governance by setting a common target to limit global warming below 2°C. That same year, the United Nations General Assembly launched the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as part of the 2030 Agenda, aiming for a universal, integrated, and comprehensive approach to development. However, political and financial challenges, including the reduced international climate commitments and the withdrawal of the United States from key agreements, have complicated efforts to achieve these goals, highlighting the need for renewed global cooperation.

1.3 Literature Review

Our study focuses primarily on the interconnections between the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Rather than treating each goal in isolation, recent literature emphasizes the empirical synergies and trade-offs that connect the various nodes and dimensions of the UN framework. We build upon the work of Jean-Pierre Cling and Clément Delecourt (2023), who adopt an exploratory framework to analyze SDG interdependencies. Using Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) on a comprehensive set of SDG indicators, they identify three principal dimensions explaining 42% of total variance: human development, environmental sustainability, and governance. Their findings support the hypothesis that SDGs are not in competition with one another : most interactions are either complementary or neutral. These results align with other contributions emphasizing the systemic structure of SDGs interlinkages and their dependence on development dynamics. David Le Blanc (2015), for instance, proposes a network-based approach, identifying certain goals ("Reduced inequalities" and "Responsible consumption and production"), as structural nodes due to their influence on multiple targets. However, these synergies in action, does not account for a sufficient SDG achievement. Despite positive interlinkages between SDGs, the 2024 UN Report notes that only 17% of SDG targets are currently on track, while a third have stagnated or regressed. While some argue that effective implementation of the SDGs should therefore relies on the prioritization of targets, particularly by identifying which goals or indicators have the strongest interconnections and multiplier effects (Cameron Allen et al, 2019); others reveal that many governments still engage in "cherry-picking," favoring economic goals such as SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth) while neglecting environmental objectives (Forestier and Kim, 2020).

This tendency to prioritize economic growth leads us to the core issue explored in our study: the relationship between economic performance and SDG achievement. Within the 2030 Agenda, economic growth is often presented as a lever to accelerate progress on multiple fronts (SDG 1, SDG 3 and SDG 4). Yet this growth-centric model increasingly appears at odds with ecological imperatives such as climate action (SDG 13) and biodiversity preservation (SDGs 14 and 15). Cling and Delecourt's Hierarchical clustering Analysis (HCA) results reinforce this tension, showing that SDG performance is strongly stratified by income level. Complementary work by Nilsson et al. (2018) highlights that the effects of growth on SDG progress are neither uniform nor unidirectional: while some goals benefit from rising GDP, through better infrastructure or services, others may face trade-offs, particularly in environmental domains. This imbalance echoes deeper tensions between economic growth and sustainability, encapsulated by the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC), which posits that environmental degradation increases in early stages of development but declines after reaching a certain income threshold. Cling and Delecourt's findings appear to reflect this dynamic. Jason Hickel (2019) argues that the growth targets embedded in SDG 8, especially the goal of 3% annual GDP growth, are fundamentally incompatible with ecological sustainability. Based on empirical data, he shows that efficiency gains alone are insufficient to reduce absolute emissions and resource extraction, and calls for a redefinition of development centered on redistribution and reduced material consumption.

Income bias appears as a first grid of SDGs stratification between countries (Cling and Delecourt 2023). Still, some actors, including Antonio Guterres, highlight governance quality and international solidarity as essential levers for progress, others point to structural and political constraints. Recent clustering analyses also invite us to consider dimensions beyond income that reflect those tendencies. Caglar (2022) identifies five country profiles based on SDG performance, revealing that governance quality, institutional capacity, and human capital are equally crucial in shaping trajectories. These findings suggest that income-based classifications fail to capture the full complexity of development pathways and should be complemented with structural and institutional indicators.

In summary, the literature converges on three main insights: (1) the critical importance of understanding SDG interdependencies; (2) the growing tension between growth-driven strategies and environmental

sustainability; and (3) the limits of income-based country classification. Our study contributes to this body of work by applying dimensionality reduction and clustering techniques to uncover structural patterns in SDG dynamics and assess their relationship to GDP per capita.

1.4 Methodology

1.4.1 Research Objectives and Hypotheses

Our project, conducted in collaboration with the London Stock Exchange Group (LSEG) as part of our Applied Statistics and Data Science course at ENSAE Paris, addresses the following central research question: *How are the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) structured among themselves, and how do they relate to countries' levels of development across the world?*

To answer this question, we build on existing literature and apply multivariate statistical techniques to SDG indicators. Our aim is to uncover underlying patterns in how these goals interact and to assess their alignment with different stages of economic development.

We formulate three main working hypotheses:

- (1) We expect to find strong positive correlations between economic indicators and social SDGs, such as health (SDG 3) and education (SDG 4).
- (2) We anticipate that dimensionality reduction techniques, particularly Principal Component Analysis (PCA), will reveal a limited number of latent factors structuring the variance across SDGs, reflecting key development dimensions such as economic prosperity, social equity, and environmental sustainability.
- (3) We expect that clustering techniques will exhibit three clusters corresponding to canonical income-level classifications (e.g., low, middle, and high income countries).

These hypotheses justify our methodological approach, which combines PCA to reduce dimensionality and hierarchical clustering to classify countries based on their sustainable development profiles. Econometric models are employed to test the relationship between economic development and SDG performance. A diagram illustrating our methodological design can be found in Appendix A.

1.4.2 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a classical linear dimension reduction technique that projects high-dimensional data onto a lower-dimensional subspace while preserving as much variance as possible.

Let $X_1, \dots, X_n \in \mathbb{R}^D$ denote a centered dataset. PCA seeks orthonormal directions w_1, \dots, w_K that maximize the variance of the data when projected onto these directions. Formally, the first principal component w_1 is obtained by solving:

$$w_1 = \arg \max_{\|w\|_2=1} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i^\top w)^2$$

Subsequent components are determined iteratively by projecting the data onto the orthogonal complement of the directions previously found.

In this study, we rely on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to uncover latent structures in countries' SDG performance. Although Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) is often used when indicators are grouped into predefined blocks (Cling and Delecourt 2022), our choice of PCA is motivated by both practical and analytical considerations. First, PCA is a non-parametric, unsupervised method that makes no assumptions about the distribution of the data or the functional form of the relationships between variables. This makes it

particularly well-suited to the structure of SDG data, which is heterogeneous in scale, quality, and origin. In addition, PCA only requires standardization of the input variables, thereby minimizing data transformation.

In contrast to MFA, which adjusts weights within pre-specified indicator groups (e.g., one per SDG), PCA treats all variables equally, allowing us to detect empirical dimensions that may transcend or reconfigure the official SDG classification. This agnostic posture is especially relevant in our context, where the interlinkages we aim to study may not be strictly aligned with the existing SDG structure.

One limitation may be specified regarding our analysis. Unlike MFA, which treats each SDG as a structured block of indicators and computes RV coefficients (defined as a multivariate generalization of the Pearson correlation between two groups of variables), PCA operates in a fully agnostic manner. It analyzes the total covariance structure without explicitly accounting for the grouping of indicators into thematic goals. As a result, PCA does not allow us to directly quantify the strength of interconnections between SDGs as cohesive entities; instead, it captures correlations across individual indicators, from which broader patterns must be inferred *ex post*.

1.4.3 Econometric Model

To deepen the understanding of the relationship between economic growth and sustainable development, we estimate the following regression model:

Using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and clustering techniques to explore the structure of data related to economic development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) will allow us to identify key differentiation axes between countries and to group them into clusters based on common characteristics.

However, these approaches are primarily descriptive: they help us uncover structural patterns in the data but do not quantify the strength of associations between variables. Regression analysis thus offers a complementary perspective, allowing us to evaluate the magnitude and direction of statistical relationships.

The objectives of the regressions are as follows:

- Quantifying the impact of economic development on SDGs : while PCA and clustering showed that certain principal components are strongly correlated with GDP per capita, we now seek to formally estimate the relationship between economic growth and specific Principal Components or SDG indicators.
- Testing whether economic growth leads to better sustainability outcomes : by running regressions, we can determine whether higher GDP per capita is associated with better SDG scores, or whether it contributes to environmental degradation.
- Controlling for additional factors : the previous analyses provided a broad structural understanding of how countries differ. Regression models allow us to control for confounding variables, ensuring that observed relationships are not driven by omitted factors such as institutional quality, population growth, or trade openness.

To address these questions, we propose the following regression models, designed to capture the relationship between economic growth and sustainability.

Theoretical model underpinning the regressions

The linear regressions performed will be based on a theoretical framework linking economic growth (measured by GDP per capita) to sustainable development outcomes.

We assume that the logarithm of GDP per capita depends linearly on a set of explanatory variables reflecting either synthetic dimensions of sustainability (Principal Components) or specific SDG indicators.

The baseline model can be expressed as follows:

$$\log(\text{GDP per capita}) = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_k + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where:

- X_k represents the explanatory variables, either principal components from PCA (Model 1) or raw SDG scores (Model 2),
- β_k are the parameters to be estimated,
- ε is the error term capturing unobserved factors.

The validity of the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation relies on several key assumptions:

- Independence of the residuals (tested using the Durbin-Watson statistic),
- Homoscedasticity, i.e., constant variance of the residuals (tested using the Breusch-Pagan test),
- Normality of the residuals (tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test).

When violations of these assumptions are detected (notably heteroscedasticity and non-normality), robust standard errors (HC3 type) are employed to ensure reliable inference.

The empirical strategy followed is therefore organized as follows:

1. Univariate and bivariate descriptive statistics,
2. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regressions,
3. Residual diagnostics and assumption testing,
4. Robustification of standard errors,
5. Variable selection using stepwise forward selection procedures.

2 Descriptive Statistics

2.1 Sources of Data and Dataset Cleaning

Our analysis relies on a proprietary dataset provided by the London Stock Exchange Group (LSEG). The raw data primarily originates from the UN Global SDG Database and is integrated and processed according to LSEG’s internal methodology, detailed in the documentation accompanying their *SDG Factor-In 2.0*¹ framework. This document also outlines the various preprocessing steps applied to the raw indicators, ensuring consistency and usability for analytical purposes.

The dataset covers:

- A significant number of countries (over 200 countries).
- +300 KPI : 266 indicators from the UN SDG database and enriched by indicators from other respected sources like the World Bank and some LSEG owned indicators in areas like energy and climate. These KPIs are grouped into the 17 SDGs and targets
- The dataset spans from 2000 to 2024

Year	Country_code	Country_name	Indicator_code	Indicator_name	Unit	Sign	Raw_val	Imputed_val	Winsor_val
2000	ABW	Aruba	BR_IND.FOSSIL.FUELELEC	Electricity production from oil, gas and coal sources (% of total)	%	-1.0	99.286351	99.286351	99.286351

Table 1: Extract from the first row of the dataset to illustrate its structure

Data Selection and Exclusions: To ensure the relevance of our dataset, we retain only countries that have at least one valid observation for the "GDP growth" indicator within the period 2000 to the present. This filtering step allows us to exclude dependencies and territories that are not pertinent to our model (e.g., La Réunion for France, Jersey for the UK). Additionally, we manually exclude certain territories that are not relevant to our analysis, such as the Netherlands Antilles, Greenland, Montserrat, New Caledonia, French Polynesia, and Sint Maarten (Dutch part), if they were not already removed in the previous filtering step. Finally, North Korea is excluded from our dataset due to concerns regarding the reliability of its statistical institutions.

Handling Missing Values: For each observation defined by a triplet (year, country, indicator), the variable `Raw_val` corresponds to the original value collected from publicly available sources. The variable `Imputed_val` was generated using a country and indicator specific linear interpolation method. Each time series, corresponding to a given indicator for a specific country between 2000 and the present, was treated individually. In addition, the `Winsor_val` variable was computed to mitigate the influence of extreme outliers, ensuring greater robustness in subsequent analyses.

Despite this initial cleaning from LSEG, residual missing values persisted. These were addressed through a two-step procedure. First, for each indicator-year combination, missing values were imputed using the mean value among countries within the same World Bank income group. For example, if a high-income country lacked a value for electricity production from fossil fuels in 2010, the mean for all high-income countries for that year was used as a replacement. Second, for the remaining 1,005 missing values, all of which concerned a single indicator in the early 2000s, mean imputation was not feasible due to insufficient data coverage. In such cases, the value from 2005 was retroactively applied to fill gaps from 2000 to 2004.

This rigorous cleaning process produced a dataset that is both comprehensive and internally consistent, enabling robust multivariate analyses of SDG performance across countries and over time. While this procedure does not affect the mean of the indicators, it reduces their variance, which in turn can attenuate their

¹<https://www.lseg.com/en/data-analytics/sustainable-finance/sovereign-climate-data>

influence in multivariate models such as PCA or regression.

Data Normalization: To ensure comparability across indicators expressed in different units—such as percentages, ratios, or binary variables—all `Winsor_val` values were standardized. This normalization was performed separately for each indicator by centering the values around their mean and rescaling them to have unit variance. As a result, each indicator contributes equally to the multivariate analysis, regardless of its original scale. This step is essential for distance-based methods such as PCA or clustering, where differences in scale can otherwise bias the results.

Data Enrichment: Throughout our analysis, in addition to the core dataset extracted from the UN Global SDG Database, we enriched our database using supplementary files provided by LSEG. The first file assigns each country a fixed income classification (e.g., "High Income", "Lower Middle Income") based on the World Bank's 2024 categorization. While this approach facilitates cross-country comparisons, it does not capture temporal changes in income status over the 2000–2024 period—a limitation we acknowledge.

A second file provides SDG scores computed using LSEG's proprietary *Factor-In*² methodology. These scores are available for each (country, year) combination and exist at multiple aggregation levels: individual SDG scores, broader "wedding cake" scores (Appendix B) and an overall SDG performance score. Additionally, each indicator is assigned a polarity sign (+1 or -1) to standardize interpretation, ensuring that higher adjusted values consistently indicate more favorable development outcomes. For example, poverty indicators are assigned a -1 sign so that lower poverty rates yield higher standardized scores, while indicators such as renewable energy share receive a +1, as higher values naturally reflect progress.

While this polarity was not directly incorporated in our Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA), the direction of correlations was interpreted in light of this sign convention to ensure accurate analysis. Particular caution was exercised with ambiguous indicators. For instance, per capita electricity consumption was assigned a -1 sign, reflecting the assumption that excessive energy use is undesirable. However, this may introduce bias in countries where low energy use results from limited access rather than environmental efficiency, potentially misrepresenting their development status.

Finally, the LSEG dataset also includes annual GDP per capita (in PPP terms) for each country, which serves as a key variable in our regression analysis and interpretation of development trajectories. PPP-adjusted GDP accounts for differences in price levels between countries, reflecting the real purchasing power of income rather than just its market exchange value. This adjustment is crucial in international comparisons: while nominal GDP per capita may overstate the economic strength of countries with strong currencies or understate it in countries with undervalued currencies, GDP in PPP corrects for the cost of living and inflation differences. For instance, a dollar in India buys more goods and services than a dollar in the US, a discrepancy that PPP captures.

²<https://www.lseg.com/en/data-analytics/sustainable-finance/sovereign-climate-data>

2.2 Data Availability

Figure 2: Data Availability by SDG, Latest Known Value

Figure 2 reveals differences in the completeness of available indicators across the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. For example, goals related to health, education, and clean energy often benefit from robust data collection systems, while SDG 5 (Gender Equality) and SDG 14 (Life Below Water) show significant data gaps. This unevenness is not accidental; it reflects both longstanding disparities in national statistical capacity and the inherent challenges of collecting data on complex or resource-intensive topics. The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2021 notes that fewer than half of all countries have internationally comparable data for some SDGs, such as climate action, where only about one in six countries report usable data, which underscores these challenges. However, to build the *SDG Factor-In model*³, LSEG only selected good quality KPIs from the UN SDG Database (recent data available, good geographical coverage, relevant, non-redundant, comparable across countries, etc). Ultimately, around 185 KPIs (out of 650 metrics) from the UN SDG Database passed the selection process. LSEG then enriched them with some 45 additional KPIs from well-established, respected sources including the World Bank, International Roads Federation, Enerdata, EMDAT, LSEG, etc.

As a result, the global geographical coverage of comparable data improved. Considering relatively recent data (2017–present) and a universe of 191 countries, the KPIs in this model have the following coverage:

- All countries: 70 % of KPIs cover at least 63 % of countries
- High-income OECD countries: 70 % of KPIs cover at least 85 % of countries
- Emerging markets: 70% of KPIs cover at least 70 % of countries

Recognizing these biases is essential. The disparities in data availability across SDGs imply that caution is warranted when drawing conclusions from the dataset.

³<https://www.lseg.com/en/data-analytics/sustainable-finance/sovereign-climate-data>

2.3 GDP per Capita and SDG Scores

Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of the overall SDG score and the log of GDP per capita for all countries. The visualisation highlights trajectories for selected countries. For instance, China’s GDP per capita (PPP-adjusted) rose from USD 3 980 in 2000 to USD 22 135 in 2023. This growth was accompanied by an increase in its SDG score from 45 to 59 over the same period.

According to the exogenous growth framework of the Solow–Swan model and the convergence hypothesis, low- and middle-income countries tend to grow at faster rates—owing to higher marginal returns to capital—and thus gradually catch up with advanced economies. In contrast, high-income countries, already close to their technology frontier and endowed with substantial capital stocks, experience smaller productivity gains and exhibit more stationary growth paths. This dynamic is clearly illustrated in Figure 3: China, India, and Rwanda display steep upward trajectories in both log GDP per capita and SDG scores over 2000–2024, whereas France and the United States show relatively flat evolutions, consistent with the expected relative stagnation of mature economies.

Figure 3: GDP per capita vs SDG score (2000–2024)

2.4 Preliminary Analysis of SDG Interlinkages

Adopting an agnostic posture, we construct two correlation matrices to preliminarily explore the interlinkages among the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Figure 4: Correlation Matrix of the LSEG SDG Scores in 2020

Figure 5: Correlation Matrix of the Best Representative Raw Indicators per SDG in 2020

The two correlation matrices presented—one based on LSEG composite SDG scores and the other on representative raw indicators⁴—offer complementary perspectives on the interlinkages among Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Both reveal strong positive correlations among core social goals (SDGs 1 to 4), suggesting that countries performing well in one human development dimension tend to perform well in others. Conversely, goals related to environmental sustainability (e.g., SDGs 14 and 15) show weaker or more inconsistent relationships, reflecting both structural trade-offs and data variability. While the matrices differ in construction method, they converge in highlighting meaningful clusters of interdependent goals. These patterns suggest that SDGs tend not to be in direct competition with one another, i.e., improving performance on one goal is typically associated with improvements in others. This is particularly evident among goals related to basic human development (e.g., SDGs 1 to 4), where strong positive correlations reflect common drivers such as state capacity, governance, or institutional effectiveness. This observed complementarity reinforces the value of dimensionality reduction techniques, such as PCA, to uncover latent development structures and identify clusters of mutually reinforcing goals.

⁴By “best representative raw indicator,” we mean the single raw indicator for each SDG that exhibits the strongest correlation with its composite SDG score.

3 Data Modelling and Analysis

3.1 Principal Component Analysis

Scree plot We performed Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on a pivoted dataset where each row represents a unique country-year observation and each column corresponds to a standardized indicator. The analysis was conducted using the normalized values presented in the Methodology section.

The analysis shows that 16 components are needed to explain 60% of the total variance in the dataset, underscoring its complexity. However, the first four components (PC1 to PC4) alone account for 43% of the variance, revealing a set of dominant development patterns. These leading components provide a reduced but informative representation of the global SDG landscape, capturing the main trade-offs and complementarities between indicators. They serve as a basis for clustering countries and interpreting the major axes of differentiation in sustainable development trajectories.

Figure 6: Explained and cumulative variance by principal component for all periods

Biplot To interpret the structure revealed by the first two principal components, we construct an enhanced biplot that combines two key elements: a correlation circle—extended beyond the unit radius to reflect high-magnitude correlations—and the temporal trajectories of selected countries in the reduced component space. This visualization serves a dual purpose. First, it allows us to identify which indicators and goals contribute most to each principal component, based on the direction and intensity of their projection. Second, it captures how countries evolve over time along these underlying development axes, offering an intuitive picture of their structural transformation.

In our case, we opted for an extended correlation circle to improve visual interpretability and alignment with country trajectories. Rather than restricting variable vectors to a radius of 1, we applied a uniform scaling factor $\alpha > 1$ to all vectors. This adjustment preserves the direction and relative magnitudes of the correlations but expands the graphical space to better match the distribution and scale of the country coordinates in the principal component space. The standard correlation circle is available in the Appendix C) allowing us to verify the direction and relative contribution of each variable within the unitary disc.

(a) PC1 vs PC2 : Economic Development and Human Capital VS Ecological Pressure and Environmental Trade-offs

(b) PC3 vs PC4 : Environmental Degradation and Human Pressure VS Urban Density and Land Use Pressure

(c) PC5 vs PC6 : Psychological Stress and Weak Labor Protections VS Social Inequality and Energy Inefficiency

Figure 7: Biplots of Principal Components 1 to 6 with Country Trajectories

Principal Component 1 – Economic Development and Human Capital The first principal component (PC1) can be interpreted as an axis of economic development. It shows strong positive correlations with variables such as log GDP per capita (0.82), SDG 1 (No Poverty, 0.73), and especially individual indicators like universal health coverage (0.91) and access to safely managed drinking water (0.91). In contrast, it is negatively associated with neonatal and infant mortality rates, both close to -0.90 , reinforcing its link with human development. PC1 thus captures a broad gradient of socio-economic progress, separating countries with high income and strong infrastructure from those facing persistent development deficits.

Principal Component 2 – Ecological Pressure and Environmental Trade-offs The second component (PC2) appears to reflect a dimension of ecological sustainability, but in an inverse manner. It is positively correlated with health-related goals, notably SDG 3 (0.19), and certain carbon-intensive indicators like CO₂ emissions per unit of manufacturing output (0.51) or reliance on fossil fuels (0.50). On the other hand, it is negatively associated with biodiversity protection (-0.50) and investment in research and development (-0.49), as well as with SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production, -0.35). This configuration suggests that PC2 contrasts industrial performance and energy intensity with environmental stewardship, positioning it as an axis of ecological pressure or environmental trade-offs.

Beyond these dominant dimensions, accounting for 35% of total variance, additional components also reveal more specialized but equally informative structures. Principal Components 3 to 6, although accounting for a smaller portion of the total variance, shed light on more targeted aspects of development.

Principal Component 3 – Environmental Degradation and Human Pressure PC3 captures the environmental consequences of human activity. It is negatively associated with SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) and SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), but strongly correlated with indicators such as exposure to fine particulate matter (0.57) and water stress (0.56). Interestingly, this component also reveals moderate negative correlations with measures of inequality, including the Gini index and the share of women in managerial roles. PC3 can therefore be interpreted as an axis of environmental degradation, highlighting contexts where unsustainable resource use and social inequality may go hand in hand.

Principal Component 4 – Urban Density and Land Use Pressure PC4 reflects a country’s spatial constraints and the intensity of land and resource use in its development model. It is positively associated with several indicators that signal demographic concentration and urban exposure: the share of land area below 5 meters elevation (0.55), the share of population in low-elevation zones (0.46), population density (0.44), and road network density (0.43). These correlations suggest that countries scoring high on this axis tend to be highly populated and infrastructure-intensive, often facing environmental vulnerability due to topography and urban pressure. In contrast, PC4 is negatively associated with indicators such as domestic material consumption per capita (−0.48) and the availability of arable land per person (−0.48), reflecting lower spatial efficiency and potential resource stress. This interpretation is well illustrated by the contrasting trajectories of Singapore and Australia. While Singapore, one of the most densely populated countries in the world, scores high on PC4, reflecting concentrated land use and infrastructure intensity, Australia’s negative PC4 position aligns with its low population density and abundant arable land per capita.

Principal Component 5 – Psychological Stress and Weak Labor Protections PC5 appears to capture a dimension of psychological vulnerability and institutional fragility. It is positively correlated with suicide mortality rate (0.51) and mortality from major non-communicable diseases (0.47), both of which can be interpreted as manifestations of chronic stress, mental health strain, or lifestyle-related pressures within societies. This interpretation is further supported by the positive correlation with adult smoking prevalence (0.39), an indicator frequently identified as a behavioral response to job-related stress (Sindelar, 2009). On the opposite side, PC5 is negatively associated with the level of national compliance with labor rights (−0.38), suggesting that weak institutional safeguards may exacerbate individual exposure to psychosocial risks. It is also negatively correlated with GDP per unit of energy use (−0.38), hinting at inefficiencies in economic systems that may reinforce this stress dynamic. Altogether, this component highlights contexts where the erosion of collective protections coincides with rising individual burdens

Principal Component 6 – Social inequality and energy inefficiency PC6 captures the intersection of inequality and environmental intensity. It is positively associated with indicators such as the proportion of people living below 50% of median income (0.44), per capita GHG emissions including LULUCF (0.42), total energy consumption per capita (0.41), and energy intensity (0.39). These correlations suggest that higher PC6 scores reflect societies where high consumption patterns coexist with significant income disparities. This is confirmed by strong negative correlations with equity-related indicators, including the income share of the bottom 10% (−0.44) and bottom 20% (−0.42). SDG-level correlations reinforce this interpretation, with SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy, −0.26) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production, −0.25) both negatively correlated with the component. These findings suggest that PC6 represents a structural dynamic in which inequality exacerbates environmental pressure—countries scoring high on this axis may be facing both distributional and ecological challenges simultaneously.

The trajectories depicted in the biplot highlight how nations may converge or diverge in their development profiles, depending on how they balance economic advancement with social and environmental sustainability. We illustrate this dynamic in greater detail through a brief case study of Rwanda.

Case Study – Rwanda: A Development Trajectory through the Lens of Principal Components

Rwanda offers a compelling example of structural transformation as observed through the evolution of its position in the principal component space. In the biplots, the country exhibits a clear rightward shift along PC1 over the 2000–2024 period, reflecting sustained improvements in economic development and human capital. This movement aligns with rising GDP per capita, expanded access to healthcare, and significant reductions in neonatal and infant mortality—dimensions heavily weighted on PC1 (World Bank, 2024; Binagwaho *et al.*, 2014). The progression supports the interpretation of this axis as a gradient of socio-economic advancement.

Simultaneously, Rwanda shows modest but upward movement along PC2, indicating increased industrial activity and energy use, which in part reflects the ecological pressures associated with rapid growth. However, the country’s relatively low carbon intensity and targeted investment in clean energy have so far prevented a pronounced negative drift on this axis. Along PC3, Rwanda shifts downward, suggesting a relative improvement in environmental health, as illustrated by reductions in PM2.5 exposure and improved water-stress management. This decline on PC3 reinforces the reading of this axis as capturing human-induced environmental pressure.

The country’s position along PC4 remains relatively stable, consistent with its geographical characteristics: high population density, but limited variation in land use dynamics over the period. On PC5, Rwanda exhibits a modest upward movement, reflecting progress in addressing social vulnerabilities and health burdens. In particular, mortality from non-communicable diseases (NCDs, e.g., cardiovascular conditions and diabetes) and suicide rates have declined. These health-sector gains are complemented by groundbreaking gender-equality reforms: constitutional and legislative quota laws have propelled Rwanda to near-gender parity in parliament and other decision-making bodies. These advances in women’s representation bolster social resilience and further shift the country’s PC5 score upward. Finally, along PC6, Rwanda’s trajectory remains flat or slightly declining, indicating that while material consumption levels have risen, income inequality remains relatively contained—preventing a move into the “unsustainable inequality” quadrant.

Rwanda’s trajectory thus illustrates how a low-income country can move consistently toward higher socio-economic development while managing, to some extent, the ecological and social trade-offs inherent in rapid growth.

Data projection We construct a graph representing the trajectory of selected countries in the space defined by the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) from our PCA analysis over the period 2000-2024. The structure of the observed trajectories suggests the presence of an Environmental Kuznets Curve (a well-known hypothesis in environmental economics stating that environmental degradation initially worsens with economic growth but improves beyond a certain level of development).

Figure 8: Trajectory of selected countries over 2000-2024 and global distribution in the PCA

The slope of each country’s trajectory provides a crucial insight: If a country moves rightward (along PC1) while maintaining or increasing its position along PC2, it indicates development without significant environmental degradation. If a country moves rightward but with a sharp decline along PC2, it suggests that its economic growth is coming at the expense of the environment.

This framework enables a quantitative assessment of whether countries embark on a path of economic growth that is sustainable or environmentally degrading.

Comparative Insight – Rwanda vs. The Gambia: Diverging Pathways from a Similar Starting Point While Rwanda’s trajectory in the principal component space illustrates a case of sustained socio-economic advancement with managed ecological trade-offs, a comparison with The Gambia reveals the diversity of outcomes among countries starting from similar conditions.

In the early 2000s, both countries occupied similar positions in the lower-left quadrant of the PC1–PC2 space, indicative of low GDP per capita, modest industrialization, and relatively limited ecological pressure. However, their trajectories diverged significantly in the decades that followed.

By 2023, The Gambia’s GDP per capita (887 USD) remained close to Rwanda’s (1,027 USD), but its average annual economic growth was much lower (3.3% vs. 7.4%), suggesting a slower pace of structural transformation. Environmentally, The Gambia has maintained very high carbon intensity in electricity production, consistently above 800 gCO₂/kWh between 2019 and 2023, while renewables accounted for less than 1% of its electricity mix over the same period (Enerdata, 2024).

Despite being internationally recognized for its climate ambition, with emissions targets rated as 1.5°C-compatible by the Climate Action Tracker, The Gambia faces serious implementation gaps. Current policies are not on track to meet national or international targets, and fossil fuels continue to dominate power generation due to insufficient investment in renewable infrastructure (Climate Action Tracker, 2021).

Unlike Rwanda, where environmental stewardship has been structurally embedded into public policy, The Gambia’s ecological outcomes appear to reflect passive conditions rather than proactive governance. For instance, while the country still maintains relatively high forest cover, this is largely due to limited land-use conversion pressure rather than conservation-driven policy (MECCNAR, 2021). Meanwhile, rising urban pollution, poor waste management, and a lack of diversification beyond tourism and agriculture undermine the country’s resilience to environmental stressors.

This contrast underscores a central lesson from the principal component framework: environmental degradation is not a necessary consequence of economic development. Rwanda’s experience illustrates how policy integration, institutional commitment, and targeted investment can support both ecological and social resilience. The Gambia, by contrast, illustrates how developmental inertia combined with implementation weaknesses may result in disproportionate environmental costs, even in low-emission, low-industrial contexts.

3.2 Clustering

PCA alone does not produce discrete classifications; it reveals directions of variation rather than clusters. To construct an interpretable country typology, we apply a range of clustering techniques—including K-Means and Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA)—to the principal component scores.

While preliminary K-Means results, performed both on fixed-year data and on the evolution of PCA scores over the 2000–2024 period, were run, the methodology retained for the main analysis is based on Hierarchical Clustering Analysis (HCA). This choice is motivated by its superior robustness in capturing nested structures and by the greater stability of results across multiple runs.

This clustering strategy allows us to capture the multidimensional complexity of development, consistent with recent literature on SDG-based classifications (Caglar and al. 2022).

3.2.1 HCA

HCA is an unsupervised learning technique that recursively groups observations into clusters based on their pairwise similarity. It produces a hierarchy of nested groupings that can be visualized using a dendrogram.

In our case, the clustering was performed on the first 16 principal components (PC1 to PC16), which capture the most significant variance in the SDG indicator space across all country-year observations. To measure the similarity between observations, we computed a pairwise Euclidean distance matrix. This metric,

widely used in continuous multivariate settings, considers the straight-line distance in the multidimensional PCA space.

Once the distance matrix was established, we used the Ward linkage method to build the hierarchical clustering dendrogram. The Ward method merges clusters based on the criterion of minimal increase in total within-cluster variance, thereby favoring compact and spherical cluster shapes. Ward method assumes that clusters are relatively homogeneous and compact in the feature space, which aligns well with the structure of PCA-transformed SDG data.

The resulting dendrogram provides a visual tool for exploring the number and structure of potential clusters and guides the interpretation of country development typologies.

Figure 9: Hierarchical clustering dendrogram of country-year observations. Clusters are formed using Ward linkage on PCA-transformed SDG data.

Three main clusters can be identified by examining the dendrogram, consistent with the theoretical foundations of hierarchical clustering, which suggest cutting the tree at its highest branches to obtain the most distinct groupings (see Kaufman and Rousseeuw, 2005; Murtagh and Contreras, 2012). This approach captures major structural differences in the data and is often favored when aiming for interpretability and robustness.

However, reducing the linkage threshold, i.e. selecting a lower cut-off in the dendrogram, can reveal a more granular partitioning of countries. Such refined classifications may diverge from conventional income-based groupings while preserving heterogeneity and meaningful separation between clusters. One can assume that country typologies built solely on income levels (e.g., low-, middle-, and high-income) often fail to reflect nuanced patterns in governance, social outcomes, or environmental performance.

Figure 10: Summary Statistics of Principal Component Scores and Income Categories by Country Group

Group	#Countries	Mean PC1	Mean PC2	GDP per capita	Low income	Lower-middle	Upper-middle	High income
1	26	-15.27	-4.17	685.64	22	4	0	0
2	25	-9.42	-0.33	2511.37	2	18	5	0
3	35	-2.21	4.02	3428.86	1	23	11	0
4	23	-0.60	2.12	6003.19	0	3	17	2
5	26	3.61	2.94	5866.26	0	3	20	3
6	27	7.21	1.23	36084.38	0	0	0	25
7	42	11.53	-4.24	42502.51	0	0	0	42
Total	204	-0.73	0.22	13868.89	25	51	53	72

In this spirit, we report the composition of seven clusters obtained by cutting the dendrogram at a distance threshold of 200. Interestingly, among high-income countries, two distinct families emerge, mostly grouped into clusters 5 and 6. Similarly, upper-middle-income countries are spread across clusters 2 and 4. This suggests that countries with similar income levels may still differ significantly in terms of their SDG-related principal component profiles. In other words, this classification reveals internal diversity within income groups that a traditional typology would overlook. We have also reported the mean PC1 and PC2 scores for all clusters, which highlight their strong discriminative power. Mean scores for the remaining components (PC3 to PC6) are left to the reader’s consultation in the Appendix D, as they do not exhibit meaningful or easily interpretable variation between groups.

Figure 11: Trajectory of countries that transitioned between clusters 2000–2024

The circular plot highlights a subset of countries whose SDG profiles evolved significantly over time, leading them to transition from one cluster to another between 2000 and 2024. These transitions are not random; they tend to reflect a shared upward trajectory in terms of structural development. For instance, countries such as Romania, Vietnam, and Bhutan exhibit progressive shifts from lower to higher clusters, which likely corresponds to improvements in economic fundamentals—particularly sustained growth in GDP per capita, infrastructure development, and investment in education and health.

This observation suggests the presence of a common development vector among these transitioning countries. While the clustering method is based on multidimensional SDG indicators, the most prominent differentiating axis (PC1) is strongly correlated with economic development, as previously shown. As such, upward movement across clusters can be interpreted as a reflection of both economic upgrading and convergence in social and environmental indicators.

These dynamic transitions contrast with more structurally stable countries whose SDG trajectories remain consistent over time. In that sense, this visualization not only reveals heterogeneity in development paths but also provides empirical support for the idea that structural transformation, particularly economic, can act as a catalyst for broader sustainable progress.

3.2.2 Clusters in lights of socioeconomic and politico-cultural structures

After obtaining the SDG-based clusters, we proceeded to characterize each cluster by examining the socioeconomic and politico-cultural structures of their member countries. This step was essential to contextualize the results and assess whether the groupings obtained through hierarchical clustering aligned with known structural characteristics.

To do so, we selected a set of control variables commonly used in the literature to differentiate countries beyond their SDG profiles. These variables were grouped into two main dimensions:

- Socioeconomic structure: including GDP per capita, income level classification, and human capital index;
- Politico-cultural structure: including indicators of governance, institutional strength, and human freedom.

Different indicators were selected and then analyzed in order to identify those that were discriminative in our clustering. The selection of the variables was based on the framework from Caglar and Gurler. To identify the most discriminating factors behind the cluster structure, we implemented two complementary methodologies: the Fisher ratio, which measures the ability of a variable to separate clusters based on the ratio of inter- to intra-cluster variance; and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), which assesses variable importance through their contribution to linear combinations that best separate groups.

Both methods consistently highlighted three key dimensions:

- the level of human capital, proxied by the *Global Competitiveness Index 4.0: 6th pillar: Skills*
- the *Government Effectiveness* indicator from the World Governance Indicators
- the *human freedom score* from the Human Freedom Index

Table 2: Fisher Ratio and LDA Importance of Selected Control Variables

Variable	Source	Fisher ratio	LDA importance
Global Competitiveness Index 4.0: 6th pillar: Skills	Global Competitiveness Report (2019)	4.59	9.06
Government Effectiveness	World Governance Indicators	2.32	4.09
Human freedom score	Human Freedom Index (2022)	0.88	5.44

These variables capture distinct yet complementary aspects of state capacity, economic inclusivity, and societal liberties. Their distributions across clusters are illustrated through boxplots in the Appendix E, providing a visual representation of how each group of countries differs along these key dimensions. Based on countries’ relative positioning on these three axes, as well as their income classification, we propose the following labeling for the clusters:

- **Cluster 1 – Low-Skills, Governmentally Inefficient, Low income States:** Mainly low-income countries with very weak skills, low human freedom, and poor governance.
- **Cluster 2 – Emerging Middle-Income Reformers:** Mostly lower-middle-income countries, with relatively higher freedom scores than their peers but lower levels of government efficiency and human capital.
- **Cluster 3 – Skills-Rising Middle-Income Authoritarians:** Lower-middle to upper-middle-income countries combining relatively strong skills and governance with very low levels of freedom.
- **Cluster 4 – Liberal Middle-Income Performers:** Mainly upper-middle-income countries with strong and homogeneous human freedom, average skill levels, and moderate governance.
- **Cluster 5 – High-Skills Transition Countries:** Countries in transition between upper-middle and high-income status, with well-developed skills and governance, but heterogeneity in levels of freedom.
- **Cluster 6 – Technocratic Advanced Economies:** High-income countries with strong institutions and skills, yet lower civil liberties than their peers.
- **Cluster 7 – Global Leaders in Skills, Freedom and Governance:** High-income countries excelling across all three dimensions—human capital, governance, and freedom.

Figure 12: Biplots of country clusters based on government effectiveness, skills (left), and human freedom (right)

¹The terminology used to label the clusters draws on conventions from international development and governance literature. Expressions such as “emerging reformers,” “technocratic states,” or “global leaders” are common in reports from the United Nations (UN DESA), the World Bank, the World Economic Forum, and in political science analyses of state capacity and freedom (Cato Institute, 2023).

Vietnam: A Case of Transition from Authoritarian Modernization to High-Skills Development

Vietnam presents a compelling example of structural transformation, transitioning from *Cluster 3 – Skills-Rising Authoritarians* to *Cluster 5 – High-Skills Transition Countries* between 2000 and 2024. This shift reflects a multidimensional improvement in human capital, institutional effectiveness, and partial liberalization of the economy.

- **Human Capital (GCI – Pillar 6: Skills):** According to the *Global Competitiveness Report 2019* by the World Economic Forum, Vietnam recorded the strongest improvement globally, rising 10 positions to rank 67th out of 141 countries. This rise underscores a significant national effort to invest in education and vocational training, boosting its workforce capacity and innovation potential.⁵
- **Government Effectiveness (WGI):** Data from the *Worldwide Governance Indicators* (World Bank) show that Vietnam’s score for government effectiveness improved from -0.58 in 1996 to +0.13 in 2023, indicating greater policy implementation capacity and better-quality public services.⁶
- **Human Freedom (Human Freedom Index):** While still limited compared to liberal democracies, Vietnam achieved a score of 6.08/10 in the *Human Freedom Index 2020*, ranking 121st out of 162. Economic freedom indicators have improved, despite continued restrictions on political and civil rights.⁷
- **GDP per Capita:** According to World Bank data, Vietnam’s GDP per capita increased from under USD 700 in the late 1980s to about USD 4,500 in 2023, reflecting sustained economic growth and a transition toward upper-middle-income status.⁸

Altogether, these indicators justify Vietnam’s reclassification from *Cluster 3*, defined by authoritarian governance with improving skills, to *Cluster 5*, which represents countries in transition toward advanced capabilities. Vietnam’s trajectory validates the internal logic of the cluster typology, showing how a country can shift from an authoritarian development model to one that combines institutional maturity, high human capital, and integration into global markets.

3.3 Linear Regressions

3.3.1 Objective and Modelling Strategy

Our aim is to model a country’s economic growth as a function of variables related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To do so, we begin by selecting a dependent variable that accurately reflects economic growth. GDP per capita PPP, expressed in international dollars, is widely recognized in the economic literature as a standard measure.

3.3.2 Selection of Explanatory Variables

Among the SDG-related variables available (derived from *LSEG’s SDG Factor-In model*), we distinguish three types of indicators:

- The first 16 principal components from a PCA on SDG score indicators
- The raw SDG scores
- The SDG performance indicators, which represent deviations between actual SDG scores and scores expected given the country’s income level

⁵World Economic Forum (2019), *Global Competitiveness Report*

⁶World Bank (2023), *Worldwide Governance Indicators*

⁷Fraser Institute and Cato Institute (2020), *Human Freedom Index*

⁸World Bank, *World Development Indicators*

As a preliminary step, we ensure that the fundamental assumptions of linear regression are satisfied before applying Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation. These assumptions include:

- Absence of multicollinearity among regressors
- A linear relationship between the explanatory variables and the dependent variable

The assumption of no multicollinearity is automatically satisfied when using principal components, as they are orthogonal by construction. We therefore initially use the principal components as regressors.

However, graphical inspection reveals that the relationship between GDP per capita and the principal components is nonlinear (bivariate analysis shows an exponential trend). In addition, GDP per capita is highly skewed. To linearize the relationships and stabilize variance, we take the logarithm of GDP per capita. We obtain the following relationship :

Figure 13: Left: Distribution of logarithm of GDP per capita PPP Right: Evolution of the logarithm of GDP per capita PPP as a function of the Economic principal component

The linearity assumption is now visually much better satisfied compared to the initial specification using the raw (non-log-transformed) GDP per capita PPP.

3.3.3 First Regression: $\log(\text{GDP per capita PPP})$ on Principal Components

We proceed by estimating a standard Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression of $\log(\text{GDP per capita PPP})$ on the 16 principal components, using an 80-20 train-test split. The results is available in figure 12 :

Table 3: OLS regression results: model summary (top) and coefficients (bottom)

OLS Regression Results						
Dependent Variable:	log_GDP_per_capita PPP					
Model:	OLS					
Method:	Least Squares					
No. Observations:	84456					
Df Residuals:	84439					
Df Model:	16					
R-squared:	0.918					
Adj. R-squared:	0.918					
F-statistic:	86210					
Prob (F-statistic):	0.00					
Log-Likelihood:	-29332					
AIC:	58700					
BIC:	58860					
Covariance Type:	HC3					

Variable	Coef	Std Err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
const	9.4385	0.001	7846.894	0.000	9.436	9.441
PC1	0.1200	0.000	981.446	0.000	0.120	0.120
PC2	-0.0098	0.000	-35.677	0.000	-0.010	-0.009
PC3	0.0081	0.000	24.081	0.000	0.007	0.009
PC4	0.0160	0.000	34.885	0.000	0.015	0.017
PC5	-0.0497	0.000	-104.912	0.000	-0.051	-0.049
PC6	0.0647	0.000	131.109	0.000	0.064	0.066
PC7	-0.0598	0.001	-103.674	0.000	-0.061	-0.059
PC8	0.0326	0.001	54.552	0.000	0.031	0.034
PC9	0.0095	0.001	14.696	0.000	0.008	0.011
PC10	0.0253	0.001	35.967	0.000	0.024	0.027
PC11	-0.0333	0.001	-38.088	0.000	-0.035	-0.032
PC12	-0.0350	0.001	-51.577	0.000	-0.036	-0.034
PC13	0.0563	0.001	81.285	0.000	0.055	0.058
PC14	-0.0211	0.001	-28.336	0.000	-0.023	-0.020
PC15	0.0291	0.001	47.280	0.000	0.028	0.030
PC16	0.0470	0.001	57.870	0.000	0.045	0.049

Figure 14: True vs. Predicted Values

The model achieves an R^2 of 0.918 on the test set, indicating very high explanatory power. However, it is crucial to validate the underlying regression assumptions *ex post*.

3.4 Economic interpretation of the principal-component coefficients

The coefficient estimates confirm that many principal components are statistically significant predictors of $\log(\text{GDP per capita})$, with p-values close to zero for nearly all regressors. The signs of the coefficients provide meaningful insights. For instance, the economic principal component (PC1), which captures overall development, is a strong positive correlate on income levels, as expected. On the other hand, some components such as the ecological component (PC2), exhibit negative coefficients, suggesting inverse relationships with GDP per capita along the dimensions they capture (e.g., environmental trade-offs).

This analysis confirms that the PCA transformation successfully uncovers latent structures that are both orthogonal and informative for explaining economic development. However, interpreting the principal components remains inherently abstract, and further mapping to original SDG variables is required to draw precise implications.

In the first linear regression (classic OLS), we have :

$$\log(\text{GDP}) = \alpha + \sum_{k=1}^{16} \beta_k \text{PC}_k + \varepsilon,$$

- **PC1 — Economic Development and Human Capital** ($\beta = 0.12$). A 1-point increase on PC1 is linked with $\approx 12\%$ higher GDP per capita PPP, showing how better health, education and infrastructure pay off economically.
- **PC2 — Ecological Pressure and Enviromental Trade-offs** ($\beta = -0.0098$). Climbing 1 points on PC2 goes with $\approx 1\%$ *lower* income per head, underscoring the growth cost of carbon-intensive, environmentally stressed development paths.
- **PC3 - Environmental Degradation and Human Pressure** ($\beta = 0.0081$). A one-point increase in PC3 leads to a $\approx 0.8\%$ rise in GDP per capita, but comes at the cost of public well-being and environmental sustainability.

- **PC4 — Urban Density and Land Use Pressure** ($\beta = 0.016$). Countries 1 points higher on PC4 — dense populations, scarce farmland but strong infrastructure — show roughly $\approx 1.6\%$ more GDP per capita PPP.
- **PC5 — Psychological Stress and Weak Labor Protections** ($\beta = -0.0497$). A 1-point rise is associated with about $\approx 5\%$ lower GDP per capita PPP, highlighting the macro-economic toll of poor mental health and fragile social safety nets.
- **PC6 — Social inequality and energy inefficiency** ($\beta = 0.0647$). Adding 1 point on PC6 — high consumption, high emissions, big income gaps — correlates with $\approx 6.5\%$ more GDP per capita PPP, reflecting the spending power of unequal, energy-hungry economies.

Key takeaway : investing in human capital and well-managed urbanisation yields the strongest economic return, whereas environmental stress and social fragility act as persistent drags on prosperity.

3.4.1 Model Optimization: Stepwise Variable Selection

To avoid overfitting and simplify the model, we implement a stepwise selection procedure that:

- Iteratively adds the most statistically significant variables based on p-values
- Stops when no remaining variable significantly improves the model (threshold: p-value ≤ 0.05)

By applying this method to our regression, we obtain the following results

Table 4: Stepwise OLS regression results: model summary (top) and coefficients (bottom)

OLS Regression Results						
Dependent Variable:	log_GDP_per_capita PPP					
Model:	OLS					
Method:	Least Squares					
No. Observations:	84456					
Df Residuals:	84439					
Df Model:	16					
R-squared:	0.918					
Adj. R-squared:	0.918					
F-statistic:	86210					
Prob (F-statistic):	0.00					
Log-Likelihood:	-29332					
AIC:	58700					
BIC:	58860					
Covariance Type:	HC3					

Variable	Coef	Std Err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
const	9.4385	0.001	7846.894	0.000	9.436	9.441
PC7	-0.0598	0.001	-103.674	0.000	-0.061	-0.059
PC1	0.1200	0.000	981.446	0.000	0.120	0.120
PC13	0.0563	0.001	81.285	0.000	0.055	0.058
PC6	0.0647	0.000	131.109	0.000	0.064	0.066
PC16	0.0470	0.001	57.870	0.000	0.045	0.049
PC8	0.0326	0.001	54.552	0.000	0.031	0.034
PC12	-0.0350	0.001	-51.577	0.000	-0.036	-0.034
PC15	0.0291	0.001	47.280	0.000	0.028	0.030
PC5	-0.0497	0.000	-104.912	0.000	-0.051	-0.049
PC4	0.0160	0.000	34.885	0.000	0.015	0.017
PC11	-0.0333	0.001	-38.088	0.000	-0.035	-0.032
PC10	0.0253	0.001	35.967	0.000	0.024	0.027
PC2	-0.0098	0.000	-35.677	0.000	-0.010	-0.009
PC14	-0.0211	0.001	-28.336	0.000	-0.023	-0.020
PC3	0.0081	0.000	24.081	0.000	0.007	0.009
PC9	0.0095	0.001	14.696	0.000	0.008	0.011

Here, the stepwise procedure does not eliminate any component. Indeed, the components are, by construction, designed to be non-redundant and to carry information. However, when using regressors that do not have this property, this method allows for selecting only the most effective ones for explaining the dependent variable. This will be precisely the case in section 3.4.1.

3.4.2 Model Interpretability: Towards More Readable Regressors

Despite its statistical performance, a principal component-based model remains difficult to interpret. We therefore test a stepwise regression (with robust standard errors) of the log-transformed GDP per capita PPP on the raw SDG scores. This alternative model is more interpretable and allows for the identification of SDG dimensions most closely associated with economic growth. A model explaining the logarithm of GDP per capita PPP using SDG scores instead of the principal components presents two main advantages :

- Interpretability: The estimated coefficients directly reflect the marginal effect of SDG performance on economic development.
- Robustness: All explanatory variables retained by the stepwise selection procedure are statistically significant, and standard diagnostics confirm the model's validity.

We obtain the following final model exhibited in table 5.

Table 5: Stepwise OLS regression results: model summary (top) and coefficients (bottom)

OLS Regression Results						
Dependent Variable:	log_PIB_per_capita_PPP					
Model:	OLS					
Method:	Least Squares					
No. Observations:	61952					
Df Residuals:	61934					
Df Model:	17					
R-squared:	0.837					
Adj. R-squared:	0.837					
F-statistic:	29400					
Prob (F-statistic):	0.00					
Log-Likelihood:	-37741					
AIC:	75520					
BIC:	75680					
Covariance Type:	HC3					

Variable	Coef	Std Err	z	P> z	[0.025	0.975]
const	7.1638	0.014	506.861	0.000	7.136	7.191
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	0.0060	0.000	33.510	0.000	0.006	0.006
Gender Equality	0.0017	0.000	8.485	0.000	0.001	0.002
Good Health and Well-being	0.0148	0.000	55.845	0.000	0.014	0.015
No Poverty	0.0053	0.000	26.577	0.000	0.005	0.006
Water and Sanitation	0.0110	0.000	54.053	0.000	0.011	0.011
Partnerships for the Goals	0.0101	0.000	71.527	0.000	0.010	0.010
Reduced Inequalities	-0.0051	0.000	-39.733	0.000	-0.005	-0.005
Zero Hunger	0.0062	0.000	38.843	0.000	0.006	0.007
Responsible Consumption and Production	-0.0104	0.000	-56.999	0.000	-0.011	-0.010
Affordable and Clean Energy	0.0033	0.000	21.898	0.000	0.003	0.004
Life on Land	0.0030	0.000	21.095	0.000	0.003	0.003
Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	0.0039	0.000	17.670	0.000	0.003	0.004
Decent Work and Economic Growth	-0.0028	0.000	-13.038	0.000	-0.003	-0.002
Sustainable Cities and Communities	-0.0012	0.000	-8.889	0.000	-0.001	-0.001
Climate Action	-0.0008	0.000	-5.637	0.000	-0.001	-0.001
Life Below Water	-0.0011	0.000	-6.931	0.000	-0.001	-0.001
Quality Education	0.0012	0.000	5.416	0.000	0.001	0.002

The model performs well in terms of predictive accuracy, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.84 and a Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 0.44 on the test set. All selected SDGs are significant, supporting the relevance of sustainable development factors in explaining economic prosperity.

We observe that all the SDGs are selected by the stepwise method. This indicates that all SDG scores are important in predicting economic growth. Although the method does not perform any variable selection in this case, it ensures that our regressors are not multicollinear, thereby confirming the validity of our model.

Interpretation: All selected SDGs are statistically significant. The positive coefficients associated with scores such as Partnerships for the Goals, Health, Water, and Education highlight the strong alignment between sustainable development and economic prosperity. Notably, some scores like Affordable and Clean Energy or Decent Work and Economic Growth show negative coefficients, suggesting diminishing returns or inverse effects under certain conditions.

On the one hand, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) exerting the strongest positive influence on GDP per capita PPP in purchasing-power-parity (PPP) terms are those concerned with health—SDG 3 Good Health and Well-being and SDG 6 Clean Water and Sanitation—as well as the goal promoting international collaboration, SDG 17 Partnerships for the Goals. Conversely, the most pronounced negative coefficients are associated with SDGs that focus on social well-being—SDG 10 Reduced Inequalities—and on environmental stewardship—SDG 12 Responsible Consumption and Production. Taken together, these coefficient estimates suggest that economic growth is contingent on a population capable of sustaining production, yet appears to be incompatible with simultaneously prioritising residents’ well-being and environmental conservation. This final model is the most robust and interpretable among all regressions conducted.

3.4.3 Limitations of SDG Scores and Performance Indicators

Raw SDG scores are biased by income level: high-income countries tend to achieve higher scores more easily than low-income countries. To mitigate this bias, LSEG proposes SDG performance indicators, which measure the deviation between a country’s actual SDG score and the average score for its income group. However, since these performance indicators are specifically constructed to be independent of income, regressing PPP-adjusted GDP per capita on SDG performance fails by design: the explanatory variables are not correlated with the target variable.

3.4.4 Temporal Dynamics Exploration

Five-year differences : In a second phase, we aimed to explore the temporal dimension of the relationship between SDGs and economic growth. Specifically, we computed five-year differences in both SDG scores and the log of PPP-adjusted GDP per capita, in an attempt to capture co-movements over time. This method was not effective because the assumption of a linear relationship between the independent variable and the regressors is not satisfied, as is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Evolution of the five-year differences logarithm of GDP per capita PPP as a function of the five-year differences Affordable and Clean energy Score

It is likely that measuring the difference over a longer period would allow for a more satisfactory regression. However, the availability of data did not allow us to conduct such an analysis. For example, investment in education only becomes visible in economic growth once the educated generation enters the workforce. There is therefore necessarily a latency of several years to take into account.

We also considered implementing a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model to evaluate how past SDG performance may influence current economic outcomes. A VAR is a method typically used on a single individual. Therefore, we decided to group our individuals into clusters in order to study a representative individual of each cluster, whose variables would be equal to the average of the variables within the cluster. However, since our time series consists of only 24 years and we are considering GDP per capita (PPP) along with the 17 SDG scores, each coefficient of a VAR with lag 1 would be estimated based on approximately 1.33 values. Clearly, this method does not work. A possible solution would be to reduce the number of explanatory variables, but with a time series of only 24 years, this approach would not be conclusive. The optimal strategy would therefore be to either find longer time series or use a panel VAR method. Since our time series cannot be extended and panel VAR is not available in Python, we have not yet explored this temporal dimension.

This remains a promising direction for future work, particularly as longer time series become available.

4 Conclusion

4.1 Discussion

Our study set out to explore the structural relationship between economic development and progress on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), relying on dimensionality reduction, clustering, and econometric modeling. The project was grounded in recent literature, particularly the work of Cling and Delecourt (2023), which highlighted SDG interdependencies and tensions between economic and environmental objectives. From the outset, our goal was to assess whether economic growth, often taken as a lever for development, aligns with sustainability across various dimensions.

Our PCA results confirmed the existence of a limited number of latent factors underlying SDG variation, with PC1 clearly capturing economic development and PC2 reflecting environmental degradation, thus supporting the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis in our data. Moreover, clustering techniques applied to PCA scores revealed nuanced development trajectories that transcend simple income-based classifications. Countries such as Vietnam demonstrated dynamic upward mobility, moving between clusters over time and underscoring the nonlinearity of development paths.

In the regression phase, we conducted two parallel models: one using principal components as predictors, and another using SDG scores directly. The final model we retained, an OLS regression of log-transformed GDP per capita (PPP) on stepwise selected SDG scores, achieved a strong adjusted R^2 of 0.837, with all included SDGs statistically significant. Interestingly, goals such as Health (SDG 3), Water and Sanitation (SDG 6), and Partnerships for the Goals (SDG 17) emerged as the strongest positive correlates of economic development. Conversely, indicators like Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8) or Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7) showed negative coefficients, possibly reflecting marginal returns or structural inefficiencies in some contexts. These results illustrate that while sustainable development and prosperity are often aligned, trade-offs persist, especially in environmental and productivity-related domains.

4.2 Future Research

While our analysis provides valuable insights, avenues for future research remain open.

First, our regression models do not yet incorporate the cluster structure identified via HCA. Including cluster-fixed effects or interaction terms could refine our understanding of how the impact of specific SDGs varies across development groups. This would help determine whether the same sustainability drivers apply equally in low-income and high-income contexts.

Second, our analysis remains static and cross-sectional, despite the availability of time-series data. Integrating dynamic econometric techniques, such as vector autoregression (VAR) or panel regressions, could allow for causal inference and temporal analysis of the progress of the SDGs in relation to economic growth. This would be particularly relevant for countries like Vietnam, whose trajectories reflect significant structural transformation over the past two decades.

Lastly, the application of machine learning methods, such as random forests or gradient boosting, could provide complementary insights into nonlinearities and interactions between SDGs and growth. However, such methods may sacrifice interpretability, which remained a priority in our study.

In sum, our results confirm the complex, multi-dimensional nature of sustainable development and the importance of structural, not just economic, determinants. They call for more nuanced, data-driven policy approaches that account for complementarities and conflicts between SDGs. This project offers a solid foundation, but further empirical refinements are needed to fully understand the pathways toward sustainable prosperity.

Appendices

A Methodological research design

Figure 16: Research design adapted from Çağlar and Gürler (2022)

B SDG Wedding Cake

Figure 17: Credit, Azote for Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University

The wedding cake model offers a new perspective on the SDGs by highlighting the interconnectedness of the environmental, social, and economic pillars, which are often viewed in isolation.

C Correlation circles

This appendix presents the correlation circles associated with the principal component analysis (PCA). Each figure below shows the projection of variables onto different pairs of principal components.

Figure 18: Correlation circle for principal components PC1 and PC2

Figure 19: Correlation circle for principal components PC3 and PC4

Figure 20: Correlation circle for principal components PC5 and PC6

D Extended Summary Statistics : Clustering Characterization

Appendix – Mean Scores for PC3 to PC6 by Cluster

Group	Mean PC3	Mean PC4	Mean PC5	Mean PC6
1	1.52	0.21	-0.10	0.27
2	-0.84	0.09	0.51	1.00
3	0.92	1.03	-0.46	-1.91
4	-4.89	-2.21	-2.24	0.79
5	0.60	-2.88	2.79	-0.28
6	0.74	3.93	-0.98	2.19
7	0.84	-0.24	-0.03	-0.51
Total	-0.16	-0.01	-0.07	0.22

Appendix – Country Membership by Cluster

Cluster 1	Afghanistan, Angola, Burundi, Benin, Burkina Faso, Central African Republic, Congo, The Democratic Republic of the, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Guinea, Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Madagascar, Mali, Mozambique, Malawi, Niger, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Sudan, Chad, Togo, Tanzania, United Republic of, Uganda
Cluster 2	Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Cameroon, Congo, Comoros, Djibouti, Gabon, Ghana, Equatorial Guinea, Haiti, Kenya, Lesotho, Mauritania, Namibia, Nigeria, Papua New Guinea, Sudan, Senegal, Sao Tome and Principe, Eswatini, Timor-Leste, Yemen, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe
Cluster 3	Bangladesh, Bhutan, Cabo Verde, Algeria, Egypt, Fiji, Micronesia, Federated States of, Indonesia, India, Iran, Islamic Republic of, Iraq, Jordan, Cambodia, Kiribati, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Lebanon, Libya, Sri Lanka, Morocco, Maldives, Marshall Islands, Myanmar, Mauritius, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Palestine, State of, Solomon Islands, Syrian Arab Republic, Tajikistan, Tonga, Tunisia, Tuvalu, Vanuatu, Samoa
Cluster 4	Belize, Bolivia, Plurinational State of, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Grenada, Guatemala, Guyana, Honduras, Jamaica, Saint Lucia, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Peru, Paraguay, El Salvador, Suriname, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of
Cluster 5	Albania, Argentina, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belarus, Chile, China, Cuba, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Republic of, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Mongolia, Malaysia, Russian Federation, Serbia, Thailand, Turkmenistan, Türkiye, Ukraine, Uruguay, Uzbekistan, Viet Nam
Cluster 6	Aruba, Anguilla, United Arab Emirates, Antigua and Barbuda, Bahrain, Bahamas, Bermuda, Barbados, Brunei Darussalam, Cook Islands, Curaçao, Cayman Islands, Hong Kong, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Kuwait, Macao, Monaco, Nauru, Oman, Palau, Puerto Rico, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Seychelles, Turks and Caicos Islands, Trinidad and Tobago, Virgin Islands, British
Cluster 7	Andorra, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Korea, Republic of, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Singapore, San Marino, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, United States

E Distribution of Selected Exogenous Variables Across Clusters

Figure 21: Distribution of log GDP per capita by cluster.

Figure 22: Boxplot of Governance Index by cluster.

Figure 23: Boxplot of Human Freedom Index (HF) by cluster.

Figure 24: Boxplot of Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) Pillars by cluster.

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